

The CERN@school Programme: Document Index

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Abstract. CERN@school is a student-led research programme that brings CERN into the classroom. This document provides an index of the documents, presentations, events, code repositories, and publications related to research and other activities associated with the programme from June 2012 to December 2016. It therefore effectively serves as a chronicle of the programme for this period, covering the national expansion of the CERN@school Timepix detector network, the launch of the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID), the TimPix project (part of ESA astronaut's Principia mission), and the integration of CERN@school with the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL) research programme. Links and references to all relevant documents, presentations, code, and data are provided where available.

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1. Introduction

CERN@school is a student-led research programme that aims to bring CERN into the classroom. It is largely based around the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector [1, 2], a device developed by the Medipix2 Collaboration[†] that enables the user to visualise and record measurements of ionising radiation in real time. As well as changing the way radiation can be explored in the classroom, data from Timepix devices deployed around the UK, in space, and at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) can also be used by CERN@school collaboration members to carry out authentic, novel scientific research suitable for publication in peer-reviewed journals.

A brief history and description of the programme may be found in the proceedings of the 37th International Conference on High Energy Physics (ICHEP 2014) [3]. Since that conference, held in July 2014, CERN@school has become a flagship programme of the Institute for Research in Schools[‡] (IRIS), a UK charity that aims to offer schools students and their teachers the opportunity to participate in real science in many different fields. This document aims to capture the progress and status of the CERN@school programme in the period from June 2012 to December 2016. This roughly corresponds to the start of the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) Science in Society Large Award (grant number ST/J000256/1) and the end of the STFC Public Engagement Fellowship (PEF) for CERN@school (grant number ST/N00101X/1). To this end, the documents, presentations, events, code repositories, and publications associated with CERN@school research, educational, and promotional activities have been indexed and are briefly described in the relevant sections and subsections of this document. Hyperlinks and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) are provided where available.

1.1. Overview of the index

Section 2 indexes the documents (Section 2.1), presentations (Section 2.2), events (Section 2.3), and code repositories (Section 2.4) related to the core CERN@school programme. This includes research-based and educational material related to the Timepix detector that has been produced as a direct result of the programme, such as the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) satellite experiment, Radiation Around You (RAY), and the UK Space Agency-backed TimPix Principia project.

Section 3 provides the same information (Sections 3.1–3.4) for items relating to the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL) experiment. This material has been given its own section as generally speaking the work reported linked to the STFC PEF and was therefore more research-focussed. The peer-reviewed publications produced as part of CERN@school and/or MoEDAL have been listed separately in Section 4. References, acronyms, and acknowledgements may be found in sections 5, 6, and 7 respectively.

[†] See <http://medipix.web.cern.ch>

[‡] See <http://researchinschools.org>

2. The CERN@school programme

As noted in the introduction, an overview of the CERN@school programme may be found in the proceedings of the 2014 International Conference of High Energy Physics (ICHEP) [3]. A brief summary of the programme's activities is provided below; the reader may then find further information in the listings of documents, presentations, events, and code (subsections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 respectively).

- **In the beginning:** CERN@school was conceived when students from the Simon Langton Grammar School for Boys visited the Medipix laboratories at CERN in 2007. After seeing the potential for using the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detectors [1, 2] for detecting and visualising ionising radiation in the classroom, a pilot project was established with the support of the South East Physics network (SEPnet) and Kent County Council (KCC) that placed ten detectors in schools around Kent, England.
- **LUCID:** Students from the Langton Star Centre, the research facility attached to the school and directed by B. Parker, then submitted a proposal for the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) experiment to a satellite competition for schools run by the British National Space Centre[†] and Surrey Satellite Technology Limited (SSTL). Consisting of five Timepix detectors arranged in an open-faced cube, LUCID was ultimately accepted as one of scientific payloads aboard SSTL's Low Earth Orbit (LEO) technology demonstration satellite, TechDemoSat-1. In 2011, the UK Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) awarded LUCID a Science in Society Large Award to support the dissemination of data and the development of educational and promotional resources for schools. In the run-up to the (delayed) launch, GEANT4 [4, 5] simulations of LUCID were performed to estimate the performance of the detector and provide training data for CERN@school students. The results of this work were presented at the CHEP 2013 [6] and iWoRID 2014 [7] conferences. On Tuesday the 8th July 2014, TechDemoSat-1 launched successfully aboard a Soyuz 2b launch vehicle from Baikonur Cosmodrome, Kazakhstan. The satellite has since been commissioned and has been delivering data for the CERN@school programme since October 2014. LUCID project leader C. Hewitt presented the first results at the 2015 National Astronomy Meeting (NAM) (see section 2.2.25).
- **The Detector Network:** With the launch of TechDemoSat-1 delayed and additional funding secured, the opportunity was taken to expand the original CERN@school detector network. Twenty-five Timepix detectors, supplied by Jablotron[‡], were procured and distributed around the UK via the Institute of Physics (IOP) Physics Teacher Network (PTN) (see section 2.2.7). Many presentations and workshops were given to introduce students, teachers, and outreach network coordinators to the Timepix technology and data management systems. In 2013, a Royal Commission for the Exhibition of 1851 Special Award was made to support the role of Schools Research Champion for this national

[†] Now the UK Space Agency (UKSA).

[‡] See <http://www.jablotron.com>

network of detectors (and LUCID). Subsection 2.3.19 describes the CERN@school Eclipse 2015 event, where many of the Timepix detectors in schools made measurements before, during, and after the total solar eclipse of Friday the 20th of March 2015 [8]. Results from this experiment, and many others including the Radiation In Schools Experiment (RISE), RAY, and Fractional Attenuation of Ionising Radiation (FAIR), were presented at the three CERN@school Research Symposia held at the University of Surrey (2014, section 2.3.16), Queen Mary University of London (2015, section 2.3.20), and the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (2016, section 2.3.24).

- **The demonstration experiments and user guides:** as the Timepix detector is a research-grade piece of scientific equipment, four classroom demonstration experiments were carried out, written up and published in peer-reviewed journals – *Physics Education* [9] and *Contemporary Physics* [10]. This was to demonstrate not only the physics but how to prepare and publish one's scientific work and results with CERN@school. User guides and instructions were also provided on the CERN@school website, which was at the time hosted by CERN[†]. The datasets from the experiments have also been made available in the [FigShare](#) online data repository (see Section 2.1). Following feedback from teachers and outreach officers, a new set of guides and demonstration experiment worksheets were prepared for IRIS by LFT Consulting and the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC). CERN@school also moved its web presence to the IRIS website, where these documents are hosted (see Section 2.1).
- **Coding with CERN@school:** The relatively simple data format used by the Timepix detector – ASCII text files containing the pixel x , y , and count values – meant that data processing and analysis with high-level programming languages like Python could be done fairly easily. CERN@school could therefore provide students (and teachers) with an introduction to coding motivated by scientific research (as opposed to making an app or other more trivial applications). To this end, various training materials featuring CERN@school data were prepared (see Section 2.1). A CERN@school [GitHub](#) educational organisation was also created and CERN@school-related code was published there, including the code used in the published CERN@school experiments. See Section 2.4 for further information and a list of relevant code repositories.
- **GridPP and the CernVM:** in October 2013, the Fellow joined the GridPP Collaboration [11, 12] as Dissemination Officer. GridPP, which represents the UK's contribution to the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG), had previously offered computing support for CERN@school via the [cernatschool.org](#) Virtual Organisation (VO). This appointment offered the opportunity to formalise this partnership. [cernatschool.org](#) acted as a technology demonstrator VO for GridPP's New User Engagement Programme. By using these technologies to power the work featured in CERN@school publications, e.g. [7], they were tested and ready for other new user communities from medical physics, astrophysics and computational biology to use in

[†] Formerly at <http://cernatschool.web.cern.ch>

their activities and increasing GridPP's engagement beyond the LHC and particle physics. Further details and case studies (of which CERN@school is one) can be found in the document described in Section 2.1.23. CERN@school students were also involved in testing and providing feedback on the GridPP UserGuide, the document described in Section 2.1.24 which provides a complete guide to getting on the Grid with GridPP. Furthermore, the GridPP CernVM – a Virtual Machine (VM) image provided by CERN configured for use with the GridPP New User Engagement Programme – can provide an out-of-the-box working environment for coding with Python and CERN@school. A document describing how to create a GridPP CernVM for use with CERN@school is described in Section 2.1.20. CERN@school was also represented at many of the GridPP Collaboration meetings in this period; see Section 2.2 for further details.

- **TimPix and Principia:** following a successful partnership for a UKSA-funded LUCID side project for primary schools, “*Whatever the Space Weather*”, L. F. Thomas (LFT Consulting) worked on behalf of the Langton Star Centre and then the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) to establish the TimPix project. Part of the UKSA Principia Mission, which coordinated the outreach activities associated with UK European Space Agency (ESA) astronaut Tim Peake's visit to the International Space Station (ISS), TimPix gave participating students access to data from the five Timepix detectors installed aboard the ISS. Students working on TimPix projects presented their work at the Summer 2016 Medipix Collaboration meeting (Section 2.3.22) and the Principia Schools Conference (Section 2.3.23). A CERN@school Timepix detector also featured in a demonstration of real-time radiation visualisation in Dr Kevin Fong's 2015 Royal Institution Christmas Lectures (Section 2.3.21).
- **The MoEDAL experiment at CERN:** owing to the students' experience with the Timepix detector, the Langton Star Centre joined the MoEDAL collaboration in 2013[†], and so CERN@school added data from a Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiment to its scientific portfolio[‡]. However, as this became the focus of the Fellow's activities from January 2015, the documents, presentations, events and code repositories have been given a dedicated section (Section 3).

2.1. Documents

Table 1 lists the documents relating to CERN@school research and activities, which are then briefly described in the following subsections. This includes things like internal reports, posters, experimental protocols, published datasets, and user guides, but not presentation slides (which are included with the relevant presentation in Section 2.2) or code repositories (which are described in Section 2.4). Peer-reviewed publications from the CERN@school programme have been listed in Section 4 and are marked with an asterisk in Table 9.

[†] See [CERN Bulletin, Issue No. 48–49/2013](#).

[‡] CERN@school@CERN, if you will.

Table 1: Documents relating to CERN@school research and activities.

DRN	Brief Title	DOI or URL
CAS-PUB-GEN-000000	The CERN@school Programme: Document Index	10.5281/zenodo.227090
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001	CERN@school Users' Guide	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001a	Alpha absorption (teachers' guide)	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001b	Beta absorption (teachers' guide)	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001m	Capturing muons (teachers' guide)	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001r	Measuring Radon (teachers' guide)	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000001x	Measuring background radiation (teachers' guide)	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000002	CERN@school Curriculum Guide	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000003	The TimPix research guide	See http://researchinschools.org/CERN
CAS-PUB-GEN-000004	CERN@school: A simple source - potassium chloride	10.6084/m9.figshare.1544499.v3
CAS-PUB-GEN-000005	The Crookes dataset (Royal Institution, June 2013)	10.6084/m9.figshare.3492527.v3
CAS-PUB-GEN-000006	Am-241 datasets for the inverse square law CERN@school paper	10.6084/m9.figshare.734262.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000007	SEPhet Student Expo, Nov. 2013 - students' poster	10.6084/m9.figshare.949631.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000008	Measuring background radiation (detailed how-to guide)	10.6084/m9.figshare.1018712.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000009	The background radiation measurement sample dataset	10.6084/m9.figshare.895961.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000010	Eclipse 2015: protocol for MX-10 detector measurements	10.6084/m9.figshare.1618851.v2
CAS-PUB-GEN-000010a	Eclipse 2015: protocol for Mk1 detector measurements	10.6084/m9.figshare.1333542.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000011	LUCID data analysis presentation (Symposium 2014)	10.6084/m9.figshare.1333543.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000012	Coding with CERN@school - plotting functions workshop	10.6084/m9.figshare.1185541.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000013	CERN@school: Setting up a CernVM	10.6084/m9.figshare.1136052.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000014	The radiation profiles experiment sample dataset	10.6084/m9.figshare.4552825.v1
CAS-PUB-GEN-000015	The attenuation of radiation sample dataset	10.6084/m9.figshare.4588276.v2
GridPP-ENG-001	GridPP: selected new user community case studies	10.6084/m9.figshare.867659.v2
GridPP-ENG-002	The GridPP UserGuide	10.5281/zenodo.220995
		10.5281/zenodo.222702

2.1.1. *The CERN@school Programme: Document Index*

- **Full title:** The CERN@school Programme: Document Index
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000000
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.227090](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.227090)

This document provides an index for selected documents, presentations, events, code repositories, and publications relating to the research and activities of the CERN@school programme from June 2012 to December 2016.

2.1.2. *CERN@school Users' Guide*

- **Full title:** CERN@school Users' Guide
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, produced by the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS), provides a guide to CERN@school for new users. It covers the operation of the detector, case studies of how it has been used in schools, information on ionising radiation and how it is detected, and how to take measurements with and analyse data from the Jabltron MX-10 Timepix detector. It was written by L. Thomas (LFT Consulting) with support from E. Cunningham (STFC), C. Shepherd (IOP), G. Steele (SSERC), T. Whyntie (QMUL), and G. Williams (IOP) and graphic design by CreativeHex.

2.1.3. *Alpha absorption (teachers' guide)*

- **Full title:** Alpha absorption (teachers' guide)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001a
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, developed in collaboration with the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC), outlines an experiment that explores what happens to the numbers of alpha particles detected by the MX-10 unit as the distance between the source and the sensor is varied and a barrier is introduced.

2.1.4. *Beta absorption (teachers' guide)*

- **Full title:** Beta absorption (teachers' guide)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001b
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, developed in collaboration with the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC), provides a two-page guide to investigating the effect of placing different barriers between the detector and a source of beta radiation on the number of particles detected by the MX-10 unit.

2.1.5. *Capturing muons (teachers' guide)*

- **Full title:** Capturing muons (teachers' guide)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001m
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, developed in collaboration with the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC), provides a two-page guide to an experiment that aims to observe the capture of a muon produced as a result of a cosmic ray interacting with our atmosphere.

2.1.6. *Measuring Radon (teachers' guide)*

- **Full title:** Measuring Radon (teachers' guide)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001r
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, developed in collaboration with the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC), provides a simple two-page guide to performing an experiment to detect and measure the properties of the decay products of Radon.

2.1.7. *Measuring background radiation (teachers' guide)*

- **Full title:** Measuring background radiation (teachers' guide)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000001x
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document, developed in collaboration with the Scottish Schools Education Research Centre (SSERC), provides a simple two-page guide to making measurements of background radiation in a given situation. A more detailed description of the same experiment can be found in CAS-PUB-GEN-000008.

2.1.8. *CERN@school Curriculum Guide*

- **Full title:** CERN@school Curriculum Guide
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000002
- **URL:** <http://researchinschools.org/CERN>

This document provides educators with information on the discovery of radiation, the properties of the different radiation types (alpha, beta and gamma), half-life, background radiation, cosmic rays and particle detection technology - i.e. those subjects relevant to the various subject specifications in the United Kingdom and Ireland.

2.1.9. *The TimPix research guide*

- **Full title:** The TimPix research guide
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000003
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1544499.v3](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1544499.v3)

This document is the research guide for the UK Space Agency-sponsored TimPix project, TimPix: monitoring Peake radiation levels with the Timepix detector. It was written by L. F. Thomas (LFT Consulting and ESERO Space Ambassador) with graphic design by CreativeHex and support from the CERN@school team. The guide aims to provide an overview of the science one needs to know to take part in CERN@school's TimPix research, part of the UKSA's Principia project that was launched to provide science education and outreach opportunities to accompany Tim Peake's mission aboard the International Space Station in 2014/15.

2.1.10. *CERN@school: A simple source - potassium chloride*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: A simple source - potassium chloride
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000004
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.3492527.v3](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3492527.v3)

This CERN@school guide, published on FigShare, presents some instructions for making a safe source of beta radiation using potassium chloride (KCl). This can then be used for testing the operation of the CERN@school Timepix detector and doing some basic analysis with the Pixelman particle counting software.

2.1.11. *The Crookes dataset (Royal Institution, June 2013)*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: William Crookes' Notebook Radiation Measurement Data
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000005
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.734262.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.734262.v1)

This is a set of data collected with a CERN@school Timepix detector suspended above one of the notebooks belonging to William Crookes. It was collected at the Royal Institution of Great Britain, who hold Crookes' notebooks in their archive, as part of Helen Arney's BIG SCIENCE event held on Tuesday 18th June 2013.

2.1.12. Am-241 datasets for the inverse square law CERN@school paper

- **Full title:** Investigating the inverse square law with the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector - Am-241 datasets
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000006
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.949631.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.949631.v1)

This zip archive contains the datasets collected for and used in the paper, 'Investigating the inverse square law with the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector: a CERN@school demonstration experiment' [9].

2.1.13. SEPnet Student Expo, Nov. 2013 - students' poster

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Particle Detector and Beta Attenuation
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000007
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1018712.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1018712.v1)

This poster presents the work completed by the 2013 SEPnet summer students during their internships with the CERN@school programme. After an introduction to CERN@school, three areas of work with the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector are discussed: particle classification, radiation profiling, and the attenuation of beta radiation by aluminium shielding. Results and conclusions are presented. This poster was first exhibited at the SEPnet Student Expo at the Royal Institution of Great Britain on Wednesday 20th November 2013.

2.1.14. Measuring background radiation (detailed how-to guide)

- **Full title:** Background Radiation Measurements with the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector: a CERN@school how-to guide
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000008
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.895961.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.895961.v1)

This document is a how-to guide for making simple background radiation measurements with the Timepix hybrid silicon pixel detector. After introducing the aims and context of the experiment, the equipment, preparatory steps, and detector settings required are listed, as well as guidelines for acquiring and managing the experimental data. Instructions for both the CERN@school Mk1 detector and the Jablotron MX-10 digital particle camera are provided. A number of areas for further investigation are then briefly discussed. The results of sample measurements taken following the procedures outlined in this guide are presented in [10].

2.1.15. The background radiation measurement sample dataset

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Background Radiation Measurements sample data set

- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000009
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1618851.v2](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1618851.v2)

This dataset contains copies of the original data used in the background radiation measurement experiment reported in [10].

2.1.16. Eclipse 2015: protocol for MX-10 detector measurements

- **Full title:** CERN@school Solar Eclipse: (V2)Protocol For Background Radiation Measurements
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000010
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1333542.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1333542.v1)

This document, written by students from the Simon Langton Grammar School for Boys, outlines the protocol developed for data capture during the solar eclipse of the 20th March 2015, and any prior tests, for use by CERN@school participants. It features the data capture procedure for the Jablotron MX-10 detector and the instructions for how to upload the data to the DAQMAP, the Data Acquisition, Management, Analysis and Presentation system used at the time.

2.1.17. Eclipse 2015: protocol for Mk1 detector measurements

- **Full title:** CERN@school Solar Eclipse: (V2)Protocol For Background Radiation Measurements (Mk1 Detectors)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000010a
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1333543.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1333543.v1)

This document, written by students from the Simon Langton Grammar School for Boys, outlines the protocol developed for data capture during the solar eclipse of the 20th March 2015, and any prior tests, for use by CERN@school participants. It features the data capture procedure for the Mk1 (red) detector and the instructions for how to upload the data to the DAQMAP, the Data Acquisition, Management, Analysis and Presentation system used at the time.

2.1.18. LUCID data analysis presentation (Symposium 2014)

- **Full title:** CERN@school: analysing data from the LUCID experiment
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000011
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1185541.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1185541.v1)

This document contains the presentation slides used at the LUCID data analysis workshop held at the CERN@school Research Symposium 2014. This took place at the University of Surrey as part of the 10th International Conference on Position Sensitive Detectors (PSD10). The workshop covered using the DAQMAP, analysing data using cluster properties and particle

identification algorithms, and some worked examples with data from LUCID simulations and the Timepix detectors onboard the International Space Station (ISS). The talk featured work from N. Shearer (IOP Summer Student 2014).

2.1.19. Coding with CERN@school - plotting functions workshop

- **Full title:** Plotting with CERN@school: an introduction to functions
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000012
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.1136052.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1136052.v1)

This document contains slides that were used in CERN@school coding workshops on plotting functions using Python and the matplotlib software suite. It introduces the user to plotting mathematical functions at a standard suitable for academic publication in a step-by-step fashion. The presentation features work by N. Shearer (IOP summer student 2014), and the function plotted as an example is the Timepix pixel calibration surrogate function as described in [13, 14].

2.1.20. CERN@school: Setting up a CernVM

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Setting up a CernVM
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000013
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.4552825.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4552825.v1)

This document provides a guide to setting up a stand-alone CernVM (CERN Virtual Machine) that can be used for computing work with the CERN@school programme. Based on Scientific Linux 6, the Virtual Machine (VM) featured can be used for data analysis, storage and management with the CERN@school software, which is available via the CernVM File System (CernVM-FS). The CernVM can also be used as a User Interface (UI) to the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG).

2.1.21. The radiation profiles experiment sample dataset

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Radiation Profiles sample dataset
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000014
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.4588276.v2](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4588276.v2)

This dataset contains copies of the original data used in the radiation profiles experiment reported in [10]. The radiation profiles in question are of a KCl sample. The dataset contains both the real data as measured by a Timepix detector and the simulated data from the GEANT4 AllPix simulations of a Timepix detector and KCl source.

2.1.22. The attenuation of radiation sample dataset

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Attenuation of Radiation sample dataset
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-GEN-000015
- **DOI:** [10.6084/m9.figshare.867659.v2](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.867659.v2)

This dataset was obtained by A. Coupe (SEPnet summer student 2013) with a Timepix hybrid silicon detector as part of an experiment to measure the attenuation of beta particles from Strontium-90 by sheets of aluminium with varying thicknesses. The experiment and its results are described in [10].

2.1.23. GridPP: selected new user community case studies

- **Full title:** The GridPP New User Engagement Programme: Selected Case Studies
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-001
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.220995](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.220995)

In this document from the GridPP Collaboration, a number of selected case studies from the GridPP's New User Engagement Programme are presented. Communities featured include those from fields like medical physics, computational biology, space and astrophysics. The services used and developed by GridPP to achieve this engagement are also briefly described. CERN@school was the flagship Virtual Organisation (VO) during the New User Engagement Programme, and contributions from the CERN@school Collaboration helped to shape the tools, software, and documentation used throughout.

2.1.24. The GridPP UserGuide

- **Full title:** The GridPP UserGuide
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-002
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.222702](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.222702)

This document, written as part of GridPP's New User Engagement Programme, aims to help new users make use of GridPP resources through the DIRAC, Ganga and CernVM suite of Grid computing technologies. The CERN@school Virtual Organisation (VO) was the flagship VO for the development, testing, and deployment of these technologies.

2.2. *Presentations*

Table 2 provides a list of selected presentations relating to the CERN@school programme from June 2012 to December 2016, i.e. the period covering the STFC Large Award, the Special Award from the Royal Commission for the Exhibition of 1851, and the CERN@school STFC Public Engagement Fellowship. These are then detailed in the following subsections, except for standard school visits (i.e. talks in schools where an overview of the programme and basic detector and data training was provided). Note that MoEDAL-related presentations are featured in Table 6 (Section 3.2).

Table 2: A list of the presentations relating to the CERN@school programme.

Date	Title
2012-10-22	School visit: the Thomas Hardy School, Dorset.
2013-01-04	ASE 2013: CERN@school teachers' workshop.
2013-01-08	BBC Stargazing Live: CERN@school and Citizen Science.
2013-01-26	CERN@school workshops for the IOP PNCs.
2013-02-06	PGCE training day at the Langton Star Centre.
2013-03-27	CERN@school at GridPP30.
2013-05-15	SEPnet Officers CERN@school training session.
2013-05-25	CERN@school detector deployment to the IOP PNCs.
2013-06-06	School visit: Sir Roger Manwood's School, Kent.
2013-06-17	School visit: the Holt School, Berkshire.
2013-06-18	Big Science at the Royal Institution ft. CERN@school.
2013-06-28	CERN@school for the IOP's Stimulating Physics (KCL SLC).
2013-07-02	CERN@school at the ESERO-UK Teacher Conference 2013.
2013-07-15	School visit: the Lampton School, London.
2013-07-16	CERN@school at the IOP Schools Outreach Support Network.
2013-09-16	School visit: Langton Star Centre.
2013-10-15	CHEP 2013: LUCID initial simulation and analysis.
2014-03-14	Uni. Kent CERN@school training session.
2014-06-11	Medipix Collaboration meeting, June 2014.
2014-06-25	iWoRID 2014: LUCID full simulation and analysis.
2014-07-03	ICHEP 2014: an overview of CERN@school.
2014-07-14	Schools coding workshop (Langton).
2014-09-08	Symposium 2014 workshop: ask the expert.
2014-09-08	Symposium 2014 workshop: LUCID data analysis.
2014-09-08	Symposium 2014 workshop: plotting functions.
2014-10-09	CERN@school at the STFC APPE, Oct. 2014.
2014-10-22	School visit: ThinkPhysics (Northumbria University).
2015-02-26	School visit: Bohunt School (at the Langton).
2015-04-30	CERN@school at GridPP34.
2015-05-14	CERN@school at the QMUL Public Engagement Celebration.
2015-05-18	CERN@school presentation for Researchers in Schools (Langton).
2015-06-09	CERN@school at the Ogden Training Day, June 2015 (Cambridge).
2015-07-06	C. Hewitt's NAM 2015 talk: first LUCID results.
2015-09-16	Symposium 2015 presentation: the TimPix project launch.

2.2.1. ASE 2013: CERN@school teachers' workshop, 2013-01-04

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Inspirational teaching with particle physics in the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Friday 04 Jan 2013, 11:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://www.ase.org.uk/conferences/previo...>

This workshop provided an introduction to the CERN@school programme, an overview of the Timepix detector, presented the various research opportunities afforded by CERN@school, and finally presented an example analysis exercise using the inverse square law demonstration experiment.

2.2.2. BBC Stargazing Live: CERN@school and Citizen Science, 2013-01-08

- **Full title:** CERN@school and Citizen Science;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 08 Jan 2013, 18:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-kent-20958593>

This workshop introduced the general public to CERN@school and the concept of Citizen Science, presenting examples from the CERN@school programme and other outreach organisations.

2.2.3. CERN@school workshops for the IOP PNCs, 2013-01-26

- **Full title:** An Introduction to CERN@school, CERN@school: the hardware, and Data Analysis and Management for Research (three presentations);
- **Date and time:** Saturday 26 Jan 2013, 09:30 (GMT);

These three presentations were given to around half of the IOP Physics Network Coordinators (PNCs) as an introduction to the CERN@school programme. Following these workshops, the decision was made to pursue the acquisition of the MX-10 Timepix detectors from Jlabtron in order to give those PNCs who wanted one a detector for their work in schools.

2.2.4. PGCE training day at the Langton Star Centre, 2013-02-06

- **Full title:** An Introduction to CERN@school and CERN@school: the hardware – PGCE day at the Langton Star Centre;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 06 Feb 2013, 09:20 (GMT);

These talks were given to PGCE students from Canterbury Christchurch University (Kent) as part of their off-site training provided by the Langton Star Centre.

2.2.5. *CERN@school at GridPP30, 2013-03-27*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: harnessing GridPP for student-driven research;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 27 Mar 2013, 09:45 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://archive.gridpp.ac.uk/gridpp30/> (slides)

This presentation introduced CERN@school to the GridPP Collaboration. A summary of the programme was presented, providing brief overviews of the Timepix detector, the Radiation Around You (RAY) experiment, and LUCID. The potential for collaboration with GridPP was then discussed, acknowledging the support to date from the Queen Mary University of London's Particle Physics Research Centre (PPRC) and associated Tier-2 cluster. Please note that a Grid certificate is required to be installed in your browser to access the slides.

2.2.6. *SEPnet Officers CERN@school training session, 2013-05-15*

- **Full title:** Getting started with the CERN@school Mk1 detector;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 15 May 2013, 10:00 (GMT);

This presentation provided training for the SEPnet Outreach Officers in the use of the CERN@school Mk1 detector.

2.2.7. *CERN@school detector deployment to the IOP PNCs, 2013-05-25*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: an introduction, the detector, and the data (three presentations and detector deployment);
- **Date and time:** Saturday 25 May 2013, 09:00 (GMT);

These three presentations were given to around half of the IOP Physics Network Coordinators (PNCs) as they received their Jablotron MX-10 detector. The meeting itself was held at the IOP headquarters, London.

2.2.8. *Big Science at the Royal Institution ft. CERN@school, 2013-06-18*

- **Full title:** Big Science: Particle Physics;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 18 Jun 2013, 18:00 (GMT);

This presentation featured as part of science comedian Helen Arney's (Festival of the Spoken Nerd) night of Big Science at the Royal Institution of Great Britain. As well as discussing particle physics, CERN, and the Large Hadron Collider, the CERN@school programme was discussed and the Timepix detector was used to visualise radiation live on stage at the famous Royal Institution lecture theatre. This is also where the Crookes dataset, taken by placing the detector above one of William Crookes's radioactive notebooks, was obtained.

2.2.9. *CERN@school for the IOP's Stimulating Physics (KCL SLC), 2013-06-28*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Friday 28 Jun 2013, 09:00 (GMT);

This presentation gave an introduction to the CERN@school programme as part of the IOP's Stimulating Physics events. The event was run by the Science Learning Centre (SLC) at King's College London (KCL).

2.2.10. *CERN@school at the ESERO-UK Teacher Conference 2013, 2013-07-02*

- **Full title:** LUCID: the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 02 Jul 2013, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://www.stem.org.uk/community/groups...> (slides)

This presentation gave an introduction to CERN@school for the attendees of the ESERO-UK Teacher Conference 2013, covering the Timepix detector, LUCID, and the wider approach to authentic research in schools.

2.2.11. *CERN@school at the IOP Schools Outreach Support Network, 2013-07-16*

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 16 Jul 2013, 09:00 (GMT);

This presentation introduced CERN@school to the IOP's Schools Outreach Support Network at their Summer 2013 meeting.

2.2.12. *CHEP 2013: LUCID initial simulation and analysis, 2013-10-15*

- **Full title:** Simulation and analysis of the LUCID experiment in the Low Earth Orbit radiation environment;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 15 Oct 2013, 14:30 (GMT);

- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/214784/> (slides)

This talk was given at the 20th International Conference on Computing for High Energy Physics (CHEP 2013), held in Amsterdam, on the simulation and analysis of the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID). The results presented [6] demonstrated that the expected data rates from the five Timepix detectors onboard LUCID should be within the transmission capabilities of TechDemoSat-1.

2.2.13. Uni. Kent CERN@school training session, 2014-03-14

- **Full title:** Getting started with the CERN@school Mk1 detector;
- **Date and time:** Friday 14 Mar 2014, 11:00 (GMT);

This presentation provided training for a number of undergraduate students at the University of Kent in the use of the CERN@school Mk1 detector, as used by the SEPnet outreach group there.

2.2.14. Medipix Collaboration meeting, June 2014, 2014-06-11

- **Full title:** CERN@school: update for the Medipix Collaboration;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 11 Jun 2014, 10:00 (GMT);

This presentation provided the Medipix Collaboration with a brief update on CERN@school activities. The meeting itself was held at the Diamond Light Source (Rutherford Appleton Laboratory).

2.2.15. iWoRID 2014: LUCID full simulation and analysis, 2014-06-25

- **Full title:** Full simulation of the LUCID experiment in the LEO radiation environment;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 25 Jun 2014, 08:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://agenda.cnaf.infn.it/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=609> (slides)

This talk at the 16th International Workshop on Radiation Imaging Detectors (iWoRID 2014) presented the results of the full GEANT4 simulations of the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) experiment. The conference proceedings may be found in [7].

2.2.16. ICHEP 2014: an overview of CERN@school, 2014-07-03

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;

- **Date and time:** Thursday 03 Jul 2014, 09:15 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://indico.ific.uv.es/indico/conferen...> (slides)

This presentation at the 2014 International Conference for High Energy Physics (Valencia, Spain) gave an overview of the CERN@school programme. The talk described the programme's history, the Timepix detector, the various experimental activities associated with the programme (including Radiation Around You, LUCID, and the demonstration experiments, the collaboration with GridPP, an estimate of the programme's impact, and an overview of future plans. The conference proceedings are reported in [3].

2.2.17. Symposium 2014 workshop: ask the expert, 2014-09-08

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Ask the Expert;
- **Date and time:** Monday 08 Sep 2014, 10:20 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/174805/sess...>

This workshop, part of the first CERN@school Research Symposium which was held at the University of Surrey, allowed attendees to get one-to-one expert advice on various aspects of the CERN@school programme, including detector operation and data management and analysis with the DAQMAP.

2.2.18. Symposium 2014 workshop: LUCID data analysis, 2014-09-08

- **Full title:** CERN@school: Analysing data from the LUCID experiment;
- **Date and time:** Monday 08 Sep 2014, 11:10 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/174805/sess...> (slides)

This workshop at the first CERN@school Research Symposium showed attendees how to go about analysing data from the LUCID experiment using the DAQMAP. Examples from the LUCID GEANT4 simulations [7] and the Timepix detectors on the International Space Station (ISS) were also shown and discussed. This workshop was prepared in collaboration with N. Shearer (IOP summer student 2014).

2.2.19. Symposium 2014 workshop: plotting functions, 2014-09-08

- **Full title:** Plotting with CERN@school: an introduction to functions;
- **Date and time:** Monday 08 Sep 2014, 11:35 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/174805/sess...> (slides)

This workshop showed attendees how to plot a function with Python from scratch using the matplotlib software suite. It was prepared by N. Shearer (IOP summer student 2014).

2.2.20. CERN@school at the STFC APPE, Oct. 2014, 2014-10-09

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 09 Oct 2014, 10:00 (GMT);

This presentation, given by B. Parker and C. Harvey, provided the STFC Advisory Panel for Public Engagement (APPE) with an update on CERN@school activities.

2.2.21. CERN@school at GridPP34, 2015-04-30

- **Full title:** The Science of CERN@school;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 30 Apr 2015, 14:35 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/369153/> (slides)

This presentation gave an update on the research activities associated with the CERN@school programme, including the new demonstration experiments, the Eclipse 2015 work, LUCID, Grid activities, and the MoEDAL experiment.

2.2.22. CERN@school at the QMUL Public Engagement Celebration, 2015-05-14

- **Full title:** CERN@school – update for the QMUL Public Engagement Celebration, May 2015;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 14 May 2015, 17:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://www.qmul.ac.uk/publicengagement/C...>

An update on the status of CERN@school was provided for Prof. John Womersley, Chief Executive of STFC, who gave the keynote presentation at the Queen Mary University of London's Public Engagement Celebration event.

2.2.23. CERN@school presentation for Researchers in Schools (Langton), 2015-05-18

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Monday 18 May 2015, 10:00 (GMT);

This presentation introduced delegates from the Researchers in Schools (RIS) programme to CERN@school in a meeting held at the Langton Star Centre.

2.2.24. CERN@school at the Ogden Training Day, June 2015 (Cambridge), 2015-06-09

- **Full title:** CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 09 Jun 2015, 09:00 (GMT);

This presentation introduced CERN@school to the Ogden Teaching Fellows and outreach officers present at the Ogden training day held at Homerton College, Cambridge.

2.2.25. C. Hewitt's NAM 2015 talk: first LUCID results, 2015-07-06

- **Full title:** LUCID - results from our cosmic ray detector on TechDemoSat-1;
- **Date and time:** Monday 06 Jul 2015, 16:25 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://nam2015.org/index.php/monday/form...>

This presentation, given by LUCID Team Leader C. Hewitt on behalf of the CERN@school Collaboration, presented the first results from the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) to the 2015 National Astronomy Meeting at Venue Cymru, Llandudno, Wales.

2.2.26. Symposium 2015 presentation: the TimPix project launch, 2015-09-16

- **Full title:** TimPix: Monitoring Peake radiation levels with the Timepix detector;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 16 Sep 2015, 11:30 (GMT);

This presentation launched the TimPix project at the second CERN@school Research Symposium, held at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). The project, funded by the UK Space Agency as part of their Principia scheme, gives students working with the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) access to data from the five Timepix detectors onboard the International Space Station (ISS).

2.3. Events

Table 3 lists events that took place between June 2012 and January 2017 that in some way involved CERN@school. Each event is then briefly described in the following subsections. Please note that, generally speaking, if there was a presentation given at an event it will be listed in Section 2.2 and may not be listed here.

Table 3: Events relating to CERN@school research and activities.

Date	Brief Title
2012-07-03	LUCID at the RSSSE 2012 (London)
2013-01-03	CERN@school at ASE 2013 (Reading)
2013-01-08	BBC Stargazing Live 2013 (Canterbury)
2013-01-26	IOP Teachers Network Full Coordinators Meeting (Canterbury)
2013-02-12	LUCID meeting at SSTL (Guildford)
2013-03-14	CERN@school at the Big Bang Fair 2013 (London)
2013-10-14	CHEP 2013 (Amsterdam, Holland)
2013-11-20	SEPnet 2013 Student Expo (Ri, London)
2014-01-08	CERN@school at ASE 2014 (Birmingham)
2014-06-11	Medipix Collaboration Meeting (Diamond Light Source)
2014-06-19	2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
2014-06-22	iWoRID 2014 (Trieste, Italy)
2014-07-02	ICHEP 2014 (Valencia, Spain)
2014-07-08	LUCID launch (Baikonur, Kazakhstan)
2014-09-07	PSD10 (Uni. Surrey)
2014-09-08	CERN@school Research Symposium 2014 (Uni. Surrey)
2014-09-24	UK ASDC National Conference 2014 (London)
2015-03-11	CERN@school at the Big Bang Fair 2015 (NEC, Birmingham)
2015-03-20	Total Solar Eclipse 2015: a CERN@school experiment
2015-09-16	CERN@school Research Symposium 2015 (QMUL)
2015-12-28	The Royal Institution Christmas Lectures 2015 (BBC4)
2016-09-21	Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN)
2016-11-02	Principia Schools Conference Nov. 2016 (Uni. Portsmouth)
2016-11-08	CERN@school Research Symposium 2016 (RAL)

2.3.1. LUCID at the RSSSE 2012 (London) – 2012-07-03

- **Full title:** Cosmic 100: LUCID at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition 2012
- **Start date:** Tuesday 03 Jul 2012
- **End date:** Sunday 08 Jul 2012
- **URL:** <http://sse.royalsociety.org/2012/exhibits/cosmic-100/>

The Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) exhibition stand was part of the Cosmic 100 display at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition 2012. The stand, designed and built by Ian Simmonds, featured a Timepix detector and a number of mildly radioactive geological sample to demonstrate the real-time visualisation capabilities of the Timepix detector, five of which would be onboard LUCID when it ultimately launched.

2.3.2. CERN@school at ASE 2013 (Reading) – 2013-01-03

- **Full title:** The ASE Annual Conference 2013 - Reading
- **Start date:** Thursday 03 Jan 2013
- **End date:** Saturday 05 Jan 2013
- **URL:** <http://www.ase.org.uk/conferences/previo...>

CERN@school attended the Association for Science Education (ASE) 2013 Annual Conference with a presence on the STFC exhibition stand and a workshop for teachers on the CERN@school detectors.

2.3.3. BBC Stargazing Live 2013 (Canterbury) – 2013-01-08

- **Full title:** BBC Stargazing Live 2013 at the Simon Langton Grammar School for Boys
- **Date:** Tuesday 08 Jan 2013
- **URL:** <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-kent-20958593>

The Simon Langton Grammar School for Boys, home of CERN@school at the time, hosted a local BBC Stargazing Live event. CERN@school featured in a session about Citizen Science.

2.3.4. IOP Teachers Network Full Coordinators Meeting (Canterbury) – 2013-01-26

- **Full title:** IOP Teachers Network Full Coordinators Meeting
- **Date:** Saturday 26 Jan 2013

The January 2013 IOP Teachers Network Full Coordinators Meeting was held at the Langton Star Centre, where around half of the Physics Network Coordinators (PNCs) were first introduced to the CERN@school programme and the Timepix detectors.

2.3.5. LUCID meeting at SSTL (Guildford) – 2013-02-12

- **Full title:** LUCID meeting with Prof. Larry Pinsky at SSTL (Guildford)
- **Date:** Tuesday 12 Feb 2013

Students from the LUCID team met with engineers from Surrey Satellite Technology Ltd. (SSTL) and Professor Larry Pinsky (Uni. Houston/NASA) to discuss plans for the launch and operation of the LUCID experiment, as well as gaining access to data from the five Timepix detectors aboard the International Space Station (ISS). The meeting was hosted by David Cooke (SSTL), Chief Engineer for SSTL on the LUCID project.

2.3.6. CERN@school at the Big Bang Fair 2013 (London) – 2013-03-14

- **Full title:** The Big Bang Fair 2013 (ExCeL, London)
- **Start date:** Thursday 14 Mar 2013
- **End date:** Sunday 17 Mar 2013
- **URL:** <http://www.stfc.ac.uk/news/big-bang-fair-2013/>

CERN@school had a presence at the Big Bang Fair 2013 (ExCeL, London) with the LUCID exhibition display stand that was used at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition 2012.

2.3.7. CHEP 2013 (Amsterdam, Holland) – 2013-10-14

- **Full title:** 20th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (Amsterdam, Holland)
- **Start date:** Monday 14 Oct 2013
- **End date:** Friday 18 Oct 2013
- **URL:** <http://www.chep2013.org/>

CERN@school attended CHEP 2013 to present the first results from simulations of the LUCID experiment. These were used to estimate the data rates that would be required for operation of the experiment in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). The results are reported in the conference proceedings which may be found in [6].

2.3.8. SEPnet 2013 Student Expo (Ri, London) – 2013-11-20

- **Full title:** The SEPnet 2013 Summer Student Expo at the Royal Institution of Great Britain
- **Date:** Wednesday 20 Nov 2013

It was at this event that SEPnet summer students J. Cook and A. Coupe presented their CERN@school summer placement poster. They won the best poster award and were presented with their prize by Prof. Jim Al-Khalili (Uni. Surrey).

2.3.9. *CERN@school at ASE 2014 (Birmingham) – 2014-01-08*

- **Full title:** The ASE Annual Conference 2014 - Birmingham
- **Start date:** Wednesday 08 Jan 2014
- **End date:** Saturday 11 Jan 2014
- **URL:** <http://www.ase.org.uk/conferences/previo...>

CERN@school attended the Association for Science Education (ASE) 2014 Annual Conference to launch its network of MX-10 detectors and latest set of education materials, with a keynote speech given by Prof. J. Butterworth (UCL) on CERN's ATLAS experiment.

2.3.10. *Medipix Collaboration Meeting (Diamond Light Source) – 2014-06-11*

- **Full title:** Medipix Collaboration Meeting (Diamond Light Source, Oxfordshire)
- **Start date:** Wednesday 11 Jun 2014
- **End date:** Thursday 12 Jun 2014
- **URL:** <http://www.diamond.ac.uk/Home/Events/2014/Medipix.html>

CERN@school attended the open portions of the June 2014 Medipix Collaboration meeting, held at the Diamond Light Source at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL). An update of CERN@school activities featuring the Timepix detector was given to collaboration members.

2.3.11. *2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN) – 2014-06-19*

- **Full title:** 2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
- **Start date:** Thursday 19 Jun 2014
- **End date:** Saturday 21 Jun 2014
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/320391>

The 2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at CERN, and CERN@school were invited to attend thanks to the students' experience with the Timepix detectors to explore whether they could contribute to the MoEDAL (Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC) experiment.

2.3.12. *iWoRID 2014 (Trieste, Italy) – 2014-06-22*

- **Full title:** 16th International Workshop on Radiation Imaging Detectors (Trieste, Italy)
- **Start date:** Sunday 22 Jun 2014

- **End date:** Thursday 26 Jun 2014
- **URL:** <https://agenda.cnaf.infn.it/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=609>

It was at iWoRID 2014 that CERN@school collaboration members presented results from the full GEANT4 simulations of the LUCID experiment. These are summarised in the conference proceedings that may be found in [7].

2.3.13. ICHEP 2014 (Valencia, Spain) – 2014-07-02

- **Full title:** 37th International Conference on High Energy Physics (Valencia, Spain)
- **Start date:** Wednesday 02 Jul 2014
- **End date:** Wednesday 09 Jul 2014
- **URL:** <http://indico.ific.uv.es/indico/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=2025>

It was at ICHEP 2014 that CERN@school was formally introduced to the international High Energy Physics (HEP) community, with an overview of the programme presented to conference delegates as part of the outreach and engagement stream. The conference proceedings may be found in [3].

2.3.14. LUCID launch (Baikonur, Kazakhstan) – 2014-07-08

- **Full title:** LUCID launches aboard TechDemoSat-1 (Baikonur, Kazakhstan)
- **Date:** Tuesday 08 Jul 2014
- **URL:** <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/science-environment-28200846>

LUCID finally launched aboard Surrey Satellite Technology Limited (SSTL) demonstration satellite, TechDemoSat-1, on a Soyuz rocket from Baikonur in Kazakhstan at 21:58 local time (16:58 BST). The launch was covered by the BBC and various other media outlets. Data was soon being received from LUCID and the first results were presented by C. Hewitt (LUCID student team leader) at the 2015 National Astronomy Meeting (NAM 2015).

2.3.15. PSD10 (Uni. Surrey) – 2014-09-07

- **Full title:** PSD10: The 10th International Conference on Position Sensitive Detectors
- **Start date:** Sunday 07 Sep 2014
- **End date:** Friday 12 Sep 2014
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/174805>

The 10th International Conference on Position Sensitive Detectors featured the latest developments in position sensitive detectors from leading researchers around the world and across a wide range of scientific disciplines. Held at the University of Surrey, PSD10 hosted the first ever CERN@school Research Symposium on Monday 8th September 2014 as part of

its scientific programme. M. Campbell, head of the Medipix Collaboration, gave the keynote address.

2.3.16. CERN@school Research Symposium 2014 (Uni. Surrey) – 2014-09-08

- **Full title:** CERN@school Research Symposium 2014 (Uni. Surrey, Guildford)
- **Date:** Monday 08 Sep 2014
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/174805/sessions/126851/#20140908>

The first ever CERN@school Research Symposium was held at the University of Surrey, Guildford, as part of the 10th International Conference on Position Sensitive Detectors (PSD). 76 students from twelve schools came from as far as Aberdeen (flying there and back in a day!) to take part, giving talks, presenting posters, and attending workshops on CERN@school related research and activities.

2.3.17. UK ASDC National Conference 2014 (London) – 2014-09-24

- **Full title:** CERN@school attends the UK ASDC National Conference 2014
- **Date:** Wednesday 24 Sep 2014
- **URL:** http://www.sciencecentres.org.uk/events/2014_Conference/

A delegation from the CERN@school team attended the UK Association for Science and Discovery Centres (ASDC) National Conference 2014, where they had an exhibition stand featuring a demonstration of the Timepix detector.

2.3.18. CERN@school at the Big Bang Fair 2015 (NEC, Birmingham) – 2015-03-11

- **Full title:** The Big Bang Fair 2015 (NEC, Birmingham)
- **Start date:** Wednesday 11 Mar 2015
- **End date:** Saturday 14 Mar 2015

Nearly 70,000 young people, teachers and parents came to The Big Bang UK Young Scientists and Engineers Fair to see science, technology, engineering and maths brought to life from 11-14 March 2015 at Birmingham's National Exhibition Centre (NEC). CERN@school featured as part of S. Sheehy's (STFC) talk with S. Gates and H. Fry entitled, *Gastronaut and the Quantum Mechanical Chocolate Factory*. A CERN@school detector was used to show the radiation emitted by different types of food. The talk was given twelve times to an audience of around 1500 people, i.e. 12,000 in all.

2.3.19. Total Solar Eclipse 2015: a CERN@school experiment – 2015-03-20

- **Full title:** Total Solar Eclipse 2015: a CERN@school experiment
- **Date:** Friday 20 Mar 2015
- **URL:** <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1333542.v1>

This event saw the first coordinated measurements taken with the CERN@school detector network as part of an experiment to observe what happened to levels of background radiation during the Total Solar Eclipse of the 20th of March 2016. Around twenty detectors were used in schools across the country to make measurements during the eclipse itself, as well as during other test and control runs. The experiment is reported in [8]. The data was uploaded originally to the DAQMAP and then to TAPAS (the Timepix Analysis Platform As School), hosted by the Langton Star Centre on behalf of the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS).

2.3.20. CERN@school Research Symposium 2015 (QMUL) – 2015-09-16

- **Full title:** CERN@school Research Symposium 2015 (Queen Mary University of London)
- **Date:** Wednesday 16 Sep 2015

The second CERN@school Research Symposium was held at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). Around 100 students from schools across the country attended, giving talks and presenting posters on their research. The keynote address was given by Professor Lawrence Pinsky (NASA/Uni. Houston) on NASA's use of Timepix detectors on the International Space Station (ISS) and Orion project. The Symposium also saw the launch of the TimPix project, part of Tim Peake's Principia mission aboard the ISS that has given students from schools in the UK and US access to data from NASA's ISS Timepix detectors.

2.3.21. The Royal Institution Christmas Lectures 2015 (BBC4) – 2015-12-28

- **Full title:** The Royal Institution Christmas Lectures 2015: How to Survive in Space (BBC4)
- **Start date:** Monday 28 Dec 2015
- **End date:** Wednesday 30 Dec 2015
- **URL:** <http://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/b06tg0b5>

The 2015 Royal Institution Christmas Lectures were given by Dr Kevin Fong, with help from the UK's first ESA astronaut Tim Peake. The series looked at how to survive in space, and featured a live demonstration of the visualisation of ionising radiation by a Timepix detector as used onboard the International Space Station (ISS) for the TimPix project. The Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) provided Windfall Films (the Christmas Lectures production company) with a CERN@school detector for demonstration purposes in what was the first use of Medipix technology on live, nationwide television.

2.3.22. Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN) – 2016-09-21

- **Full title:** Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN)
- **Date:** Wednesday 21 Sep 2016
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/570934/>

CERN@school attended the open session of the September 2016 Medipix Collaboration meeting, held at CERN. An update of CERN@school activities featuring the Timepix detector was given by IRIS students to collaboration members, including reports from LUCID, TAPAS, Autonaut and TimPix.

2.3.23. Principia Schools Conference Nov. 2016 (Uni. Portsmouth) – 2016-11-02

- **Full title:** Principia Schools Conference Nov. 2016 (Uni. Portsmouth)
- **Date:** Wednesday 02 Nov 2016
- **URL:** <https://principia.org.uk/schools-conferences/portsmouth/>

The UK Space Agency and its educational partners celebrated the imaginative work linked to Tim Peake's Principia mission done by children of all ages at a pair of conferences for young people. The conference held at the University of Portsmouth covered those in the south of England. CERN@school students attended to showcase their work on the TimPix project, which featured data from the five Timepix detectors onboard the International Space Station (ISS). CERN@school detectors were also used at the conference to demonstrate the Timepix technology used to monitor Tim Peake's radiation levels in real time.

2.3.24. CERN@school Research Symposium 2016 (RAL) – 2016-11-08

- **Full title:** CERN@school Research Symposium 2016 (Rutherford Appleton Laboratory)
- **Date:** Tuesday 08 Nov 2016

The third CERN@school Research Symposium was held at STFC's Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in Didcot, Oxfordshire. Around 100 students from schools across the country attended, giving talks and presenting posters on their research, as well as participating in visits and tours around the RAL Harwell campus. The keynote address was given by head of the Medipix Collaboration Michael Campbell (CERN), and other talks featured updates on Radiation Around You (RAY), LUCID, the Timepix Analysis Platform At School (TAPAS, the replacement data management system for the DAQMAP), TimPix, and the CERN@sea collaboration with Autonaut Ltd.

2.4. Code repositories

In order to ensure students could freely participate in CERN@school-related scientific studies, all software and analysis code required to analyse data from the Timepix detectors was made publicly available via the online code repository [GitHub](https://github.com). When CERN@school existed as a separate entity, CERN@school used the CERN@school GitHub Organization:

<http://github.com/CERNatschool>

as a place for hosting software repositories that were undergoing active development. GitHub kindly provided an Educational Account for CERN@school which meant that a limited number of private repositories could be kept too. However, with the creation of the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS), a new GitHub Organization was created for software development across all IRIS projects:

<http://github.com/InstituteForResearchInSchools>

and the CERN@school Organization has since been decommissioned. As a number of the repositories featured code used in the CERN@school documents and publications, the repository will remain on the GitHub website but will no longer be active. Except where otherwise noted, the software is issued under an MIT software license and may be used by IRIS students (or indeed anyone else) as required. Furthermore, stable releases of these repositories have been published on the CERN-backed [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/) repository which assigns them a permanent DOI. The relevant repositories are listed in Table 4 and detailed in the following subsections.

Table 4: Code repositories associated with CERN@school research and activities.

Host	Organisation	Repository Name	Section
http://github.com	CERNatschool	LUCIDITY	2.4.1
http://github.com	CERNatschool	SimLUCID-lite	2.4.2
http://github.com	CERNatschool	beta-attenuation	2.4.3
http://github.com	CERNatschool	cluster-sorter	2.4.4
http://github.com	CERNatschool	fast-cluster-analysis	2.4.5
http://github.com	CERNatschool	frame-viewer	2.4.6
http://github.com	CERNatschool	get-coding	2.4.7
http://github.com	CERNatschool	getting-started	2.4.8
http://github.com	CERNatschool	inverse-square-law	2.4.9
http://github.com	CERNatschool	particle-rate-plotter	2.4.10
http://github.com	CERNatschool	public-doc-index	2.4.11

2.4.1. LUCIDITY: simulation management web app

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/LUCIDITY>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.250180](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.250180)

The Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector Interactive Test sYstem (LUCIDITY) is a web app for running and managing simulations of the LUCID detector. It is based on the Hobo Ruby on Rails framework and was used to carry out the research reported in the CHEP 2013 conference proceedings [6].

2.4.2. SimLUCID-lite: first simulations of LUCID in LEO

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/SimLUCID-lite>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.246650](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.246650)

SimLUCID-lite is a simple GEANT4-based simulation of the Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector (LUCID) experiment, used to estimate the expected data rates observed in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). This is the official initial release of the SimLUCID-lite code that accompanies the CHEP 2013 conference proceedings [6], with an updated README.md to link CERN@school with the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS).

2.4.3. CERN@school: beta attenuation with aluminium

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/beta-attenuation>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.262584](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.262584)

This repository contains the code and data needed to recreate the analysis carried out for the beta radiation attenuation experiment described in Section 5 of the CERN@school Contemporary Physics paper [10]. The datasets featured in the paper are included with the code, but may also be found on FigShare (CAS-PUB-GEN-000015).

2.4.4. CERN@school: cluster sorting code

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/cluster-sorter>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.261151](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.261151)

This repository contains code for analysing, visualising and sorting clusters of pixels measured by the Timepix detector using the techniques described in [10].

2.4.5. *Fast Cluster Analysis for Timepix data*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/fast-cluster-analysis>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.262642](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.262642)

The code in this repository can be used to perform a fast cluster analysis on data collected with a Timepix detector for use in research conducted as part of the CERN@school programme. An example analysis using the radiation profile methods described in Section 4 of the CERN@school Contemporary Physics paper [10] is included. The datasets featured in the paper are included with the code, but may also be found on FigShare (CAS-PUB-GEN-000014).

2.4.6. *The CERN@school Frame Viewer*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/frame-viewer>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.260078](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.260078)

This repository contains some simple Python code for displaying CERN@school Timepix frame data using a GridPP CernVM and the matplotlib software suite.

2.4.7. *Get Coding with CERN@school!*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/get-coding>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.260081](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.260081)

This repository contains the Jupyter notebooks and code associated with the prototype CERN@school coding course. It contains one lesson that may be used as a basis for others and further development of the course. The lesson displays in GitHub as a Jupyter notebook, but also may be used interactively when downloaded and run on (for example) a GridPP CernVM.

2.4.8. *Getting started with CERN@school (legacy training code)*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/getting-started>

- **Latest release:** v2.0

- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.258966](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.258966)

This repository contains legacy code associated with training material for the CERN@school programme; see (for example) CAS-PUB-GEN-000012. This initial release has been updated to reflect CERN@school's move to the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS).

2.4.9. *Testing the inverse square law with CERN@school: analysis code*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/inverse-square-law>

- **Latest release:** v2.1
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.260103](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.260103)

This repository contains the code required for performing the analysis described in the CERN@school inverse square law experiment, as described in [9]. The dataset used in the paper is available separately at doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.949631.v1.

2.4.10. *CERN@school: particle rate plotter*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/particle-rate-plotter>

- **Latest release:** v2.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.262541](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.262541)

This code is for estimating the mean rate of particles detected with a Timepix detector using the method described in Section 3 of the CERN@school Contemporary Physics paper [10] and the accompanying background radiation measurement how-to guide (CAS-PUB-GEN-000008) on FigShare. There is also code for plotting the time profile (i.e. the number of pixels detected over a time series) for a given dataset for a given day. The datasets featured in the paper are included with the code, but may also be found on FigShare (CAS-PUB-GEN-000009).

2.4.11. *The CERN@school Programme: Document Index (LaTeX code)*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/public-doc-index>

This repository contains all of the code needed to generate the CERN@school public document index, i.e. this document.

3. MoEDAL

The Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC [15] is the seventh major experiment at CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC). It is housed underground at Interaction Point (IP8), sharing the experimental cavern with the LHCb experiment. MoEDAL is designed to probe the LHC's particle collisions for signs of Paul Dirac's hypothesised magnetic monopole, as well as other highly ionising signs of new physics that the other LHC experiments cannot easily look for. A full introduction to the MoEDAL experiment may be found in document CAS-PUB-MDL-000002 (see Section 3.1.2) and an accompanying bibliography in CAS-PUB-MDL-000001 (see Section 3.1.1); the reader is advised to consult these for more information about MoEDAL itself.

The Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) is a full member of the MoEDAL Collaboration, with the Langton Star Centre having joined in 2013 owing to their experience with the Timepix detectors. Students and teachers associated with IRIS have access data from the MoEDAL experiment and are able to contribute to the MoEDAL Collaboration's research programme. With the expansion of the CERN@school team under IRIS, it was decided that from January 2016 the Fellow should focus on research activities with the MoEDAL Collaboration. These included:

- **Collaboration activities:** as with any LHC experiment, there were many collaboration activities that the Fellow was required to perform as part of the role. These included the biannual Collaboration Meetings and various trips to CERN. As a member of the Software and Analysis Group (SaAG), there were also the SaAG meetings every other week. All of these meetings, with brief summaries, are listed in the Presentations and/or Events sections. Furthermore, there were various promotional activities undertaken on behalf of the Collaboration. These included the Monopole Quest! exhibit at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition (see Section 3.3.4), various schools talks, and an article published via The Conversation which was read by over half a million people (see Section 3.1.5).
- **The Timepix detector network:** funding for two Timepix detectors for deployment in the LHCb cavern was secured from STFC. This deployment has been managed by the University of Alberta on behalf of CERN@school (and so IRIS). As full collaboration members, CERN@school also has access to the Timepix detector network managed by the Czech Technical University (CTU), Prague. Data from this network, which was operational during Runs I and II of LHC operations, has been used as the basis of studies by IRIS and MoEDAL CERN summer school students which forms the basis of the MoEDAL internal note, "*On the flora and fauna of highly ionising background radiation at Interaction Point 8*". Further details may be found in Section 3.1.10.
- **The Nuclear Track Detectors and Monopole Quest!:** as with all research programmes, new developments and opportunities led to a slight shift in direction for the Fellow's activities. While CERN@school's expertise originally focussed on the Timepix detector,

it was suggested that the thousands of visitors to the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition (RSSSE) could be engaged with MoEDAL's research by helping to analyse scanned images from the Nuclear Track Detectors (NTDs). With this in mind, a Zooniverse Citizen Science project was designed and created by IRIS students using the Panoptes project builder. This enabled volunteers (at the RSSSE or elsewhere) to identify and measure etch pits and other features in scans from NTD plastic exposed to the LHC radiation environment and heavy ion test beams. The results from this formed the basis of a pilot study reported in a MoEDAL internal note (see Section 3.1.11). Furthermore, a guide to MoEDAL (CAS-PUB-MDL-000002) and accompanying educator presentation template (CAS-PUB-MDL-000004) were prepared to facilitate the use of Monopole Quest! in a classroom context. Details of these can be found in Sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.4 respectively.

- **MoEDAL software and the Grid:** towards the end of 2016, the Fellow also established the MoEDAL Virtual Organisation (VO) on the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) which enabled both MoEDAL and CERN@school researchers to make use of GridPP's computing resources. Following this, and a successful run of simulations used in the analysis of 13 TeV data from the Magnetic Monopole Trapper (MMT) subdetector system, the Fellow was appointed Software Coordinator for the MoEDAL Collaboration. As part of the duties associated with this role, the MoEDAL Grid User Guide (CAS-PUB-MDL-000006) and `moedal-run-simulations` repository were created; these are detailed in Sections 3.1.6 and 3.4.8 respectively. MoEDAL also featured as a case study for GridPP's New User Engagement Programme. MoEDAL (and LHCb) software is available to IRIS students via CVMFS on a GridPP CernVM.

As a member of the MoEDAL Collaboration, the Fellow was also included on the MoEDAL author list. Associated publications are listed in Section 4. These include the first physics results from the MoEDAL experiment as reported in the Journal of High Energy Physics (JHEP) [16] and Physical Review Letters (PRL) [17]. The reader may also be interested in the CERN@school bibliography (CAS-PUB-MDL-000001), which contains a fairly comprehensive set of references relating to MoEDAL and many other searches for magnetic monopoles. Further details may be found in Section 3.1.1.

3.1. Documents

Table 5 lists the documents relating to MoEDAL research and activities supported by IRIS. A brief description of each is provided in the following subsections.

Table 5: Documents relating to MoEDAL research and activities.

DRN	Brief Title	DOI or URL
CAS-PUB-MDL-000001	The MoEDAL bibliography	10.5281/zenodo.193038
CAS-PUB-MDL-000002	A guide to MoEDAL	10.5281/zenodo.248615
CAS-PUB-MDL-000003	Maxwell's Equations	10.5281/zenodo.215308
CAS-PUB-MDL-000004	Presentation template	10.5281/zenodo.255318
CAS-PUB-MDL-000005	Article for The Conversation	10.5281/zenodo.248601
CAS-PUB-MDL-000006	Grid user guide	10.5281/zenodo.255649
CAS-PUB-MDL-000007	Dirac's monopole (figure)	10.5281/zenodo.215523
CAS-PUB-MDL-000008	Dipole vs. monopole (figure)	10.5281/zenodo.215520
CAS-PUB-MDL-000009	2012 Timepix array (figure)	10.5281/zenodo.167056
CAS-INT-MDL-000001	Timepix internal note	MoEDAL Twiki page
CAS-INT-MDL-000002	NTD internal note	MoEDAL Twiki page

3.1.1. The MoEDAL bibliography

- **Full title:** The CERN@school programme: MoEDAL bibliography
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000001
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.193038](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.193038)

This document presents a bibliography of publications relating directly or indirectly to the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL). It is intended to serve as a reference for members of the MoEDAL Collaboration, students involved in research activities connected to MoEDAL, and indeed anyone with an interest in the latest searches for Dirac's hypothesised magnetic monopole at CERN's Large Hadron Collider. Both quick reference summary tables, indexed by BibTeX citation code (as used in the accompanying BibTeX file), and a full bibliography in the BibTeX unsrt style are provided.

3.1.2. A guide to MoEDAL

- **Full title:** The CERN@school Programme: A Guide to the MoEDAL Experiment
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000002
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.248615](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.248615)

The MoEDAL experiment (Monopoles and Exotics Detector at the LHC) is the seventh major experiment at CERN's Large Hadron Collider. It is designed to probe the LHC's particle collisions for signs of Paul Dirac's hypothesised magnetic monopole, as well as other highly

ionising signs of new physics that the other LHC experiments cannot easily look for. The Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) is a full member of the MoEDAL Collaboration, and students associated with IRIS have access data from the MoEDAL experiment and are able to contribute to the MoEDAL Collaboration's research programme. This document aims to provide a brief guide to the history, theory, and physics of the MoEDAL experiment so that IRIS students and teachers can take full advantage of these opportunities.

3.1.3. *Maxwell's Equations*

- **Full title:** Maxwell's equations with and without magnetic charge
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000003
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.215308](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.215308)

Maxwell's equations of classical electromagnetism are presented, in Gaussian units, without and with magnetic charge. Equations 5 to 8 are taken from the front cover of the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL) Technical Design Report, the Large Hadron Collider's seventh major experiment and the latest venture to be undertaken in the search for Dirac's hypothesised magnetic monopole.

3.1.4. *Presentation template*

- **Full title:** The CERN@school Programme: MoEDAL outreach talk template
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000004
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.255318](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.255318)

This Microsoft PowerPoint file contains a set of slides that may be used as a template for outreach talks by teachers, students, or scientists working with the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL) through the Institute for Research in Schools. It should be used in conjunction with The CERN@school Programme: A Guide to the MoEDAL Experiment referenced below. Users should ensure that all placeholder text (e.g. name, institution, event - and all information in the headers and footers) is amended appropriately before use. All content is issued under a Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 license except where otherwise noted: users are positively encouraged to amend, adapt, and share their own versions of the talk to suit their own style and purpose. Please also note that two images from CERN (the LHC aerial view and the Standard Model figure) need to be downloaded separately; links to the CERN Document Server (CDS) are provided on the slides in question for convenience.

3.1.5. *Article for The Conversation*

- **Full title:** Is this the end of particle physics as we know it? Let's hope not
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000005

- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.248601](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.248601)

This article, about the restart of CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and the search for magnetic monopoles at the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL), was originally published by The Conversation on June 5, 2015 6.12am BST. It was syndicated by various outlets including IFL Science and phys.org, and as of 16th January 2017 it had been viewed 500,750 times.

3.1.6. *Grid user guide*

- **Full title:** The CERN@school Programme: MoEDAL Grid User Guide
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000006
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.255649](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.255649)

This document provides a guide to getting on the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) with the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL). It covers what is required to get started on the Grid, how MoEDAL is integrated with the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid infrastructure, and how to run MoEDAL simulations using the GridPP DIRAC system and Ganga User Interface.

3.1.7. *Dirac's monopole (figure)*

- **Full title:** Dirac's magnetic monopole (figure)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000007
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.215523](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.215523)

This figure shows a schematic representation of Dirac's magnetic monopole. The monopole is imagined to be the end point of a semi-infinitely long, infinitesimally thin solenoid known as a Dirac string, shown from the side (red lines). The magnetic field lines (black arrows) are shown emanating from the point at the end of the string (imagine the red lines are infinitely close together). If such Dirac monopoles exist, it is the requirement that the string is undetectable that means electric charge must be quantised.

3.1.8. *Dipole vs. monopole (figure)*

- **Full title:** A magnetic dipole and a magnetic monopole (figure)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000008
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.215520](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.215520)

This figure shows a magnetic dipole with North and South poles (left) and a magnetic monopole, North pole only (right).

3.1.9. 2012 Timepix array (figure)

- **Full title:** Schematic of the MoEDAL Timepix detector array (2012)
- **DRN:** CAS-PUB-MDL-000009
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.167056](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.167056)

This figure shows a schematic of the MoEDAL Timepix Detector Array as of 2012 (not to scale), showing: a) Timepix detector F04-W0098 (sensor perpendicular to the beam); b) the LHCb (IP8) cavern wall; c) the LHC beam pipe; d) the LHCb VELO subdetector casing; e) Timepix detector F03-W0098 (sensor parallel to the beam).

3.1.10. Timepix internal note

- **Full title:** On the flora and fauna of highly ionising background radiation at Interaction Point 8
- **DRN:** CAS-INT-MDL-000001
- **URL:** <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/MoEDAL/MoEDALTimepixIRISFloraAndForna>

This internal note will present the initial results of both CERN@school students and MoEDAL CERN Summer students from studies of data from the MoEDAL Timepix detector network. A classification scheme for clusters observed in data from the LHC's Run I is proposed and applied to a subset of the data, and the potential for analysing the beam conditions from the Timepix readout for data from Run II and beyond is discussed.

3.1.11. NTD internal note

- **Full title:** A pilot study of mass-participation methodologies for Nuclear Track Detector analysis with the MoEDAL experiment
- **DRN:** CAS-INT-MDL-000002
- **URL:** <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/MoEDAL/MoEDALNTDCitizenSciencePilot>

This internal note will present the initial results from a pilot study involving CERN@school students on the use of mass-participation methodologies (a.k.a. Citizen Science) as applied to analysis of the MoEDAL Nuclear Track Detector scans. It features the first measurement derived from the Monopole Quest! Zooniverse project, launched at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition 2015, which took NTD scan data as processed by Bristol-based Track Analysis Systems Limited (TASL) and used the Panoptes Zooniverse project builder to create an etch pit identification and measurement system for volunteers to use. The results from this study should feed into the collaboration-wide physics paper on the NTD results from LHC Runs I and II. The repository also features the data from the first batch of Monopole Quest! results required to extract this and other results necessary for the analysis.

3.2. *Presentations*

Table 6 lists the presentations given as part of the Fellow's work with the MoEDAL Collaboration. Each one is then briefly described in the following subsections. Please note that the MoEDAL Software and Analysis Group (SaAG) and MoEDAL Collaboration meetings are only available to MoEDAL Collaboration members with the appropriate credentials. If access is required, please contact the Institute for Research in Schools[†].

Table 6: A list of the MoEDAL-related presentations given by the Fellow. Collaboration meeting presentations are indicated with an asterisk.

Date	Title
2015-03-18	MoEDAL and the Zooniverse I: Introduction.
2015-04-14	MoEDAL and the Zooniverse II: Update.
2015-04-28	MoEDAL and the Zooniverse III: Timepix data I.
2015-05-26	MoEDAL and the Zooniverse: NTD requirements.
2015-06-18 *	Zooniverse citizen science interfaces for the MoEDAL experiment.
2016-02-03	Monopole Quest! Some initial analysis.
2016-02-24	Monopole Quest! Single Blob Analysis.
2016-03-10	Panoptes TASL Scan Analysis Update.
2016-03-24	Monopole Quest! Single Blob Analysis II.
2016-04-20	The Helsinki NTD scans: a first look.
2016-05-04	The Helsinki NTD scans: Dataset preparation I.
2016-05-18	The Helsinki NTD scans: Dataset preparation II.
2016-06-01	Getting started with MoEDAL computing.
2016-06-22	Monopole Quest! Pre-collaboration meeting rehearsal.
2016-06-29 *	Monopole Quest! 5th Collaboration Meeting presentation.
2016-08-24	The TASL NTD scans: PoC study first results.
2016-09-28	Getting MoEDAL on the Grid.
2016-10-12	Update on MoEDAL grid running.
2016-12-08	Preview of Collaboration Meeting talks.
2016-12-12 *	NTD analysis update.
2016-12-13 *	Report of the Software Group.
2016-12-13 *	Update on the Timepix student-led analysis.

[†] <http://researchinschools.org>

3.2.1. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2015-03-18*

- **Full title:** MoEDAL and the Zooniverse: Harnessing Citizen Science for new physics searches;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 18 Mar 2015, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/379551/> ([slides](#));

This presentation contained an overview of the Zooniverse and its Panoptes toolkit (used for creating user-defined projects), suggested plans for using Citizen Science with the MoEDAL experiment (as well as potential uses of the Grid), and some questions for the Collaboration about the data that can be expected from the experiment.

3.2.2. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2015-04-14*

- **Full title:** MoEDAL and the Zooniverse: First steps with Timepix data;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 14 Apr 2015, 13:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/387422/> ([slides](#));

This presentation provided an update on progress with Panoptes (implementing basic workflow functionality), a brief summary of the Prague CTU datasets and their conversion to the Mafalda ROOT format, and a brief update on the status of Grid activities.

3.2.3. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2015-04-28*

- **Full title:** MoEDAL, GridPP and the Zooniverse: Citizen Science with Timepix data I;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 28 Apr 2015, 13:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/390747/> ([slides](#));

This presentation provided an overview of a demonstration Panoptes project featuring Timepix data from LHC Run I.

3.2.4. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2015-05-26*

- **Full title:** MoEDAL, GridPP and the Zooniverse: Requirements on NTD data;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 26 May 2015, 13:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/396521/> ([slides](#));

This presentation provided a brief update on the Panoptes project status and some questions about NTD data requirements.

3.2.5. *Collaboration Meeting 2015-06-18*

- **Full title:** Zooniverse citizen science interfaces for the MoEDAL experiment;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 18 Jun 2015, 10:40 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/389924/> (slides);

This presentation provided an update to the Collaboration about the status of the Panoptes projects for MoEDAL, the Timepix and NTD TASL datasets, and MoEDAL's presence on the Grid.

3.2.6. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-02-03*

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! Some initial analysis;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 03 Feb 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/492780/> (slides);

This presentation provided a first look at the classification data from the first run of the Monopole Quest! Citizen Science project. Summaries of the project and the initial dataset were presented, before looking at a brief analysis of a single image (two blobs).

3.2.7. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-02-24*

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! Single Blob Analysis;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 24 Feb 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/502949/> (slides);

This presentation provided an analysis of a single image with a single blob, employing a heat map to look at the position of a blob identified by users and extract a radius measurement.

3.2.8. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-03-10*

- **Full title:** Panoptes TASL Scan Analysis Update;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 10 Mar 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/506323/> (slides);

This was not actually a presentation with slides, but notes were written up and posted on the meeting page. The update covered the analysis of the Summer 2015 classifications and some initial tests of OpenCV and CellProfiler on the TASL NTD scan images.

3.2.9. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-03-24

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! Single Blob Analysis;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 24 Mar 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/512520/> (slides);

This presentation provided a brief update on the cataloging of the TASL datasets - both images and classifications. There are also links to the start of the accompanying paper on the use of mass-participation methodologies for the analysis of MoEDAL NTD data.

3.2.10. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-04-20

- **Full title:** The Helsinki NTD scans: a first look;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 20 Apr 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/518504/> (slides);

This presentation presented some observations made from a first look at two images from the Helsinki group's scanner. Properties of the image files were listed, along with some nice comparisons with real-world examples. The LHC vs. non-LHC features were discussed, including the so-called LHC fog, as well as some non-heavy ion fragment features from the LHC sample. Some questions for the Collaboration were posed for discussion.

3.2.11. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-05-04

- **Full title:** The Helsinki NTD scans: Dataset preparation I;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 04 May 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/526295/> (slides);

This presentation presented a first look at the Helsinki NTD scan data, including: how to split up the scan images (with links to the code), the channel content of the RGB images, the effect of the LHC fog, and a first look at applying manual thresholds.

3.2.12. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-05-18*

- **Full title:** The Helsinki NTD scans: Dataset preparation II;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 18 May 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/532794/> (slides);

This presentation contained a second look at automated processing of the Helsinki NTD data. The red and blue channels of both LHC-exposed and non-LHC exposed plastic were histogrammed to see if anything suggested itself. The pixel values from the background (i.e. non-etch pits) appear to be normally distributed, which could be useful in terms of applying a threshold to identify etch pits automatically.

3.2.13. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-06-01*

- **Full title:** Getting started with MoEDAL computing;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 01 Jun 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/538949/> (slides);

This presentation provided an overview of getting started with MoEDAL computing, using materials from the CERN@school programme. It covered getting a GridPP CernVM and using software on CVMFS to look at some Timepix detector data (including some MoEDAL frames).

3.2.14. *Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-06-22*

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! Status of Citizen Science-driven searches for new physics with the MoEDAL experiment;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 22 Jun 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/545050/> (slides);

This presentation was a rehearsal for the June 2016 MoEDAL Collaboration meeting, which presented a summary of the Monopole Quest! results to-date and a first look at the Helsinki NTD scan images.

3.2.15. *Collaboration Meeting 2016-06-29*

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! Status of Citizen Science-driven searches for new physics with the MoEDAL experiment;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 29 Jun 2016, 12:30 (GMT);

- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/493401/> ([slides](#));

This presentation was given at the 5th MoEDAL Collaboration Meeting (June 2016) to provide the Collaboration with an update on the Monopole Quest! Citizen Science studies on Nuclear Track Detector (NTD) analysis. It covers initial results from the Summer 2015 run of Monopole Quest! and a first look at the Helsinki NTD scan images.

3.2.16. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-08-24

- **Full title:** The TASL NTD scans: a Proof-of-Concept study for the MoEDAL experiment;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 24 Aug 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/564491/> ([slides](#));

This presentation presented the first measurement obtained with from the Summer 2015 run of the Monopole Quest! Citizen Science project. The measurement in question is the etch pit radius from test beam Fe fragments in plastic that has been exposed to the Interaction Point 8 radiation environment.

3.2.17. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-09-28

- **Full title:** Getting MoEDAL on the Grid;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 28 Sep 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/572200/> ([slides](#));

This presentation provided a brief introduction to getting MoEDAL users on the Grid, covering the MoEDAL VO, the MoEDAL CVMFS repository, and running the MoEDAL simulation software from a GridPP CernVM.

3.2.18. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-10-12

- **Full title:** Update on MoEDAL grid running;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 12 Oct 2016, 14:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/576267/> ([slides](#));

This presentation provided an update on running MoEDAL simulations via the Grid. The production runs for the MMT 2013 are described, as well as providing a reminder of how to join the Grid.

3.2.19. Software & Analysis Meeting 2016-12-08

- **Full title:** Preview of Collaboration Meeting talks (Timepix, NTDs, and Software);
- **Date and time:** Thursday 08 Dec 2016, 15:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/593421/> (slides);

This presentation provided a preview of the talks given at the 6th MoEDAL Collaboration Meeting on behalf of the Institute for Research in Schools.

3.2.20. Collaboration Meeting 2016-12-12

- **Full title:** Report on Progress with the Study Mass Participation Analysis of MoEDAL NTDs;
- **Date and time:** Monday 12 Dec 2016, 15:05 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/558903/> (slides);

This presentation summarised the work on the Nuclear Track Detector analysis, culminating in the first result from the Mass Participation Methodology (a.k.a. Citizen Science) Monopole Quest! Zooniverse project. This result was a measurement of the etch pits caused by iron ions from the NBL test beam recorded in NTD plastic exposed to the 8 TeV LHC radiation environment.

3.2.21. Collaboration Meeting 2016-12-13

- **Full title:** Report of the Software Group;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 13 Dec 2016, 08:35 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/558903/> (slides);

This presentation reported on the Software group's activities, including getting MoEDAL on the Grid, running the 13 TeV simulation campaign for the 2016 MMT paper, and the outlook and plans for 2017.

3.2.22. Collaboration Meeting 2016-12-13

- **Full title:** Timepix and Mass Participation Methodologies;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 13 Dec 2016, 11:30 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/558903/> (slides);

This presentation gave an update on the student-led analysis of the 2012 Timepix network data, including an update on the cluster classification scheme, identification algorithms, and potential for machine learning applications.

3.3. Events

Table 7 lists MoEDAL-related events that have taken place since CERN@school first became involved with the experiment. The events themselves are then briefly described in the following subsections. Note that for MoEDAL, this includes school visits, student workshops, and other outreach and engagement-focussed events. It should also be noted that the first MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (also held at CERN) was not officially a collaboration meeting, being more of a monopole physics workshop. Regardless, it occurred before CERN@school was involved with the experiment so is not included in the list of MoEDAL/CERN@school events.

Table 7: Events relating to MoEDAL research and activities.

Date	Brief Title
2014-06-19	2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
2014-12-10	Cluster analysis workshop/T2K visit (Langton)
2015-06-18	3rd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
2015-06-30	MoEDAL at the RSSSE 2015
2015-12-10	4th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
2016-05-02	MoEDAL: Fellow's visit to CERN
2016-06-28	5th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (Uni. Valencia)
2016-07-01	RAL Work Experience Talk: MoEDAL and the LHC
2016-09-21	Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN)
2016-12-12	6th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)

3.3.1. 2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN) – 2014-06-19

- **Full title:** 2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
- **Start date:** Thursday 19 Jun 2014
- **End date:** Saturday 21 Jun 2014
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/320391>

The 2nd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at CERN, and CERN@school were invited to attend owing to the students' experience with the Timepix detectors to explore whether they could contribute to the MoEDAL experiment. (Note: this event is the same as that described in the CERN@school section, repeated here for consistency.)

3.3.2. Cluster analysis workshop/T2K visit (Langton) – 2014-12-10

- **Full title:** CERN@school: analysing clusters from the MoEDAL experiment
- **Date:** Wednesday 10 Dec 2014

This workshop introduced the students at the Langton Star Centre to analysing clusters from the MoEDAL Timepix detector network through coding. The preliminary cluster classification scheme was described, as was its potential application to the MoEDAL experiment. There was also a presentation from S. Short (Particle Physics Research Centre, Queen Mary University of London) on her work with the T2K neutrino experiment and the importance of coding in modern High Energy Physics.

3.3.3. 3rd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN) – 2015-06-18

- **Full title:** 3rd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
- **Start date:** Thursday 18 Jun 2015
- **End date:** Friday 19 Jun 2015
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/389924/>

The 3rd MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at CERN, just before the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition where MoEDAL had an exhibition stand. This gave the collaboration a chance to see the CERN@school students' work and the materials that had been prepared for the Monopole Quest! exhibit and accompanying Zooniverse project.

3.3.4. MoEDAL at the RSSSE 2015 – 2015-06-30

- **Full title:** Monopole Quest! at the Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition 2015
- **Start date:** Tuesday 30 Jun 2015
- **End date:** Sunday 05 Jul 2015
- **URL:** <http://sse.royalsociety.org/2015/monopole-quest/>

The MoEDAL Collaboration had a stand at the 2015 Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition. This included the launch of the Monopole Quest! Citizen Science project for the analysis of Nuclear Track Detector scans using the Zooniverse's Pantopes project builder platform.

3.3.5. 4th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN) – 2015-12-10

- **Full title:** 4th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
- **Start date:** Thursday 10 Dec 2015
- **End date:** Friday 11 Dec 2015
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/459042/>

The 4th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at CERN. CERN@school students attended remotely from the Langton Star Centre via Vidyio and updated the collaboration with preliminary results from the Citizen Science studies of Timepix and Nuclear Track Detector (NTD) data from the MoEDAL experiment.

3.3.6. MoEDAL: Fellow's visit to CERN – 2016-05-02

- **Full title:** MoEDAL: Fellow's visit to CERN
- **Start date:** Monday 02 May 2016
- **End date:** Thursday 05 May 2016

During this visit to CERN, the Fellow held meetings with the spokesperson of the MoEDAL Collaboration (J. Pinfold) and members of the Open Cosmics team, as well as attending the MoEDAL Software and Analysis Group (SaAG) meeting at CERN.

3.3.7. 5th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (Uni. Valencia) – 2016-06-28

- **Full title:** 5th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (Uni. Valencia)
- **Start date:** Tuesday 28 Jun 2016
- **End date:** Wednesday 29 Jun 2016
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/493401/>

The 5th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at the Scientific Park ('Parque Científico') in Valencia, where the Instituto de Física Corpuscular (IFIC) is located. It was where the first results from the Nuclear Track Detector (NTD) analysis with the Monopole Quest! Zooniverse project were presented to the collaboration.

3.3.8. RAL Work Experience Talk: MoEDAL and the LHC – 2016-07-01

- **Full title:** MoEDAL and the LHC: the Hunt for Magnetic Monopoles

- **Date:** Friday 01 Jul 2016

This talk was given to students from the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory's work experience scheme, covering the physics of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and the hunt for magnetic monopoles there with the MoEDAL experiment. It also covered the theoretical justification for the search for isolated magnetic charge and the history of experimental searches to date.

3.3.9. Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN) – 2016-09-21

- **Full title:** Medipix Collaboration Meeting – Open Session (CERN)
- **Date:** Wednesday 21 Sep 2016
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/570934/>

CERN@school attended the open session of the September 2016 Medipix Collaboration meeting, held at CERN. As well as updates from CERN@school, the trip to CERN allowed for meetings with other members of the MoEDAL Collaboration (including Prof. J. Pinfeld) to coordinate Timepix and Nuclear Track Detector (NTD) activities.

3.3.10. 6th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN) – 2016-12-12

- **Full title:** 6th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting (CERN)
- **Start date:** Monday 12 Dec 2016
- **End date:** Tuesday 13 Dec 2016
- **URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/558903/>

The 6th MoEDAL Collaboration meeting was held at CERN. It was at this meeting that the first measurement from the Monopole Quest! Zooniverse project was presented to the collaboration. The meeting also saw Queen Mary University of London (QMUL) apply to join the MoEDAL Collaboration.

3.4. Code repositories

The shared code repositories used for work on the MoEDAL experiment are listed in Table 8. The code required to generate various public guides and documents has been archived on the CERN@school GitHub repository:

<http://github.com/CERNatschool>

Active analysis code and MoEDAL data cannot reside in the public domain (at least until the associated results have been published by the MoEDAL collaboration). The corresponding repositories are therefore hosted on CERN's GitLab system available to those with CERN computing accounts. MoEDAL's repositories are hosted here:

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/moedal/>

Students and teachers who have got as far as requiring access to the non-public MoEDAL data should contact IRIS about obtaining a CERN computing account and joining the MoEDAL Software and Analysis Group.

Table 8: Code repositories associated with MoEDAL research and activities.

Host	Organisation	Repository Name	Section
http://github.com	CERNatschool	maxwells-equations	3.4.1
http://github.com	CERNatschool	moedal-bibliography	3.4.2
http://github.com	CERNatschool	moedal-cernatschool-guide	3.4.3
http://github.com	CERNatschool	moedal-grid-user-guide	3.4.4
https://gitlab.cern.ch	moedal	moedal-iris-ntd-note-001	3.4.5
https://gitlab.cern.ch	moedal	moedal-iris-timepix-note-001	3.4.6
https://gitlab.cern.ch	moedal	moedal-plots	3.4.7
https://gitlab.cern.ch	moedal	moedal-run-simulations	3.4.8

3.4.1. Maxwell's equations with and without magnetic charge (LaTeX)

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/maxwells-equations>

- **Latest release:** v1.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.215291](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.215291)

This LaTeX code was used to generate the figures used in CERN@school's MoEDAL-related material that feature Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism with and without magnetic charge. The equations are produced as a standalone PDF document that may be used as required.

3.4.2. *The CERN@school MoEDAL bibliography*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/moedal-bibliography>

- **Latest release:** v1.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.193037](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.193037)

This repository contains the code used to generate the CERN@school MoEDAL bibliography, a list of publications relating directly or indirectly to the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL). The bibliography is intended to serve as a reference for members of the MoEDAL Collaboration, students involved in research activities connected to MoEDAL, and indeed anyone with an interest in the latest searches for Dirac's hypothesised magnetic monopole at CERN's Large Hadron Collider. As such, the BibTeX file found within may be used when writing new papers that need to reference previous research in the field.

3.4.3. *The CERN@school Programme: A Guide to the MoEDAL Experiment*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/moedal-cernatschool-guide>

- **Latest release:** v1.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.255371](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.255371)

This repository contains all of the LaTeX code needed to generate the CERN@school programme's guide to the MoEDAL experiment (CAS-PUB-MDL-000002-v1.0), and this is the initial release of the license-friendly image version. Two images from CERN need to be retrieved from the CERN Document Server (CDS); instructions for doing this are included in the README.md file provided.

3.4.4. *The CERN@school Programme: MoEDAL Grid User Guide*

<http://github.com/CERNatschool/moedal-grid-user-guide>

- **Latest release:** v1.0
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.258918](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.258918)

This repository contains all of the LaTeX code needed to generate the CERN@school programme's guide to getting on the Grid with MoEDAL (CAS-PUB-MDL-000006-v1.0).

3.4.5. *IRIS NTD internal note*

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/moedal/moedal-iris-ntd-note-001>

This repository contains everything needed for the internal analysis note on the Citizen Science-based analysis of data from the MoEDAL Nuclear Track Detectors (NTDs). It is largely based

on work by school students from the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) and some of the CERN MoEDAL Summer Students.

3.4.6. IRIS Timepix internal note

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/moedal/moedal-iris-timepix-note-001>

This repository contains everything needed for the internal analysis note on the MoEDAL Timepix detector network, based on work by done by school students from the Institute for Research in Schools (IRIS) and CERN MoEDAL Summer Students.

3.4.7. MoEDAL: Plots

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/moedal/moedal-plots>

This repository contains code for generating plots for the MoEDAL Collaboration. In this release, this includes a prototype exclusion plot and detector acceptance plot for monopole mass vs. magnetic charge for spin zero and spin half monopoles (Drell-Yan production).

3.4.8. MoEDAL: Run Simulations

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/moedal/moedal-run-simulations>

This repository contains code for running GEANT4 simulations of the MoEDAL experiment using software deployed via the CernVM File System (CernVM-FS). The simulations may be run locally or on the Grid via the Ganga Grid User Interface and the GridPP DIRAC system. Further information may be found in the MoEDAL Grid User Guide (CAS-PUB-MDL-000006).

4. Publications

The peer-reviewed publications associated with and/or referenced by the CERN@school programme are listed with full bibliographic citations in the References section. For convenience, the **BibTeX** citation code used in this document's **BibTeX** file, DOI or URL, brief notes, year of publication and citation number are listed in Table 9. Papers that were directly supported by either STFC grant number ST/J000256/1 (Science in Society Large Award, plus extensions) or STFC grant number ST/N00101X/1 (Public Engagement Fellowship) are marked with an asterisk.

Table 9: Publications associated with and/or referenced by the CERN@school programme.

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Medipix2det2002	10.1109/TNS.2002.803788	The Medipix2 detector paper.	2002	[18]
GEANT42003	10.1016/S0168-9002(03)01368-8	The main GEANT4 paper.	2003	[4]
GridPP2006	10.1088/0954-3899/32/1/N01	The key paper to cite for GridPP-related work.	2006	[11]
GEANT42006	10.1109/TNS.2006.869826	GEANT4 developments and applications.	2006	[5]
Timepix2007	10.1016/j.nima.2007.08.079	The original Timepix detector paper.	2007	[1]
TimepixErratum2008	10.1016/j.nima.2007.11.003	Corrections to the original Timepix paper.	2008	[2]
Jakubek2008	10.1016/j.nima.2008.03.091	Jakubek et al.'s first paper on Timepix calibration.	2008	[13]
Granja2008	10.1109/NSSMIC.2008.4774721	Timepix for fission fragment studies.	2008	[19]
MoEDAL2009	https://cds.cern.ch/record/1181486	The MoEDAL Technical Design Report.	2009	[15]
GridPP2009	10.1098/rsta.2009.0036	The other key paper to cite for GridPP-related work.	2009	[12]
Jakubek2009a	10.1016/j.nima.2009.03.171	Timepix for ultra-cold neutron studies.	2009	[20]
Jakubek2009b	10.1109/NSSMIC.2009.5402420	Timepix for fast neutron studies.	2009	[21]
Jakubek2010	10.1109/NSSMIC.2010.5874118	Timepix hadron therapy fragment studies.	2010	[22]
Jakubek2011	10.1016/j.nima.2010.06.183	Jakubek et al.'s precision Timepix calibration work.	2011	[14]
Urbar2011	10.1016/j.nima.2010.06.168	Cosmic balloon flights with Timepix detectors.	2011	[23]
Teyssier2011	10.1016/j.nima.2010.12.114	Timepix: electrons vs. photons.	2011	[24]
Esposito2011	10.1016/j.nima.2011.01.148	Timepix for electron microscopy/imaging.	2011	[25]
Bouchami2011	10.1016/j.nima.2010.06.163	Pattern recognition with Timepix tracks.	2011	[26]
Vilalta2011	10.1088/1742-6596/331/3/032052	More pattern recognition for Timepix tracks.	2011	[27]
Pinsky2011	10.1016/j.nima.2010.06.323	Timepix in space.	2011	[28]
Medipix2012	10.1016/j.nima.2011.09.021	Timepix charged particle tracking.	2012	[29]
Pinsky2012	10.1109/AERO.2012.6187011	Timepix in space - featuring LUCID.	2012	[30]
Whyntie2013	10.1088/0031-9120/48/3/344	The inverse square law demonstration experiment.*	2013	[9]
Whyntie2014	10.1088/1742-6596/513/2/022038	First simulations of LUCID in LEO (CHEP 2013).*	2014	[6]
Whyntie2015a	10.1088/1748-0221/10/03/C03043	Full simulations of LUCID in LEO (iWORID 2014).*	2015	[7]
Whyntie2015b	10.1080/00107514.2015.1045193	Three more demonstration experiments.*	2015	[10]
MoEDAL2016a	10.1007/JHEP08(2016)067	MoEDAL's MMT results (8 TeV).*	2016	[16]
Whyntie2016a	10.1080/10619127.2015.1104132	An update in Nuclear Physics News.*	2016	[8]
Whyntie2016b	10.1016/j.nuclphysbps.2015.09.202	The CERN@school overview paper (ICHEP 2014).*	2016	[3]
MoEDAL2017a	10.1103/PhysRevLett.118.061801	MoEDAL's MMT results (13 TeV).*	2017	[17]

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6. Acronyms

APPE Advisory Panel for Public Engagement

CERN Organisation Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire

CHEP The International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics

CTU Czech Technical University in Prague

CVMFS CernVM File Service

DOI Digital Object Identifier

ESA European Space Agency

FAIR Fractional Attenuation of Ionising Radiation (CERN@school experiment)

ICHEP International Conference of High Energy Physics

IFIC Instituto de Fisica Corpuscular

IOP Institute of Physics

IRIS The Institute for Research in Schools

ISS International Space Station

iWoRID International Workshop on Radiation Imaging Detectors

JHEP Journal of High Energy Physics

KCL King's College London

LEO Low Earth Orbit

LHC Large Hadron Collider

LHCb The Large Hadron Collider Beauty experiment

LUCID Langton Ultimate Cosmic ray Intensity Detector

MoEDAL Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC

MMT Magnetic Monopole Trapper (MoEDAL subdetector)

NAM National Astronomy Meeting

NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NTD Nuclear Track Detector (MoEDAL subdetector)

PEF Public Engagement Fellowship

PNC Physics Network Coordinator (c.f. PTN)

CAS-PUB-GEN-000000-v1.0

PPRC The QMUL Particle Physics Research Centre
PRL Physical Review Letters
PTN The IOP Physics Teacher Network
QMUL Queen Mary University of London
RAL The Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
RAY Radiation Around You (CERN@school experiment)
RISE Radiation In Schools Experiment (CERN@school experiment)
RSSSE Royal Society Summer Science Exhibition
SaAG The MoEDAL Software and Analysis Group
SEPnet South East Physics network
SLC Science Learning Centre
SSERC Scottish Schools Education Research Centre
SSTL Surrey Satellite Technology Limited
STFC Science and Technology Facilities Council
UKSA UK Space Agency
VM Virtual Machine
VO Virtual Organisation
WLCG Worldwide LHC Computing Grid

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[†] And exceptional croissants fourré crème pâtissière.

[‡] Girls are admitted in the sixth form.

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Version History

Table 10: Version history.

Version	Description	DOI	Author
1.0	Initial version.	10.5281/zenodo.227090	TW

[†] See <https://github.com/ganga-devs/>